

Institutional and Professional Challenges Affecting Service Delivery in Public Libraries: A Study of the Niger State Public Library, Nigeria

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Abstract

Public libraries play a crucial role in providing free access to information, supporting education, and promoting community development, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. However, many of these institutions are constrained by institutional and professional challenges that limit effective service delivery. This study examined the institutional and professional challenges affecting service delivery in the Niger State Public Library and identified measures for improvement. A descriptive survey design was used, involving all 51 professional and paraprofessional staff through total enumeration. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. Findings revealed that public libraries are constrained by inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, lack of modern ICT facilities, shortage of qualified personnel, limited access to up-to-date information resources, weak policy implementation, and low public awareness of library services. The study also found that library personnel faced professional challenges such as poor working conditions, inadequate training opportunities, limited ICT skills, heavy workloads, low motivation, resistance to technological change, and limited government support for staff welfare and training. The study further identified adequate funding, improved staff welfare, enhanced digital infrastructure, continuous professional training, stronger policy implementation, and increased public awareness as major strategies for improving library service delivery. The study concludes that both institutional and professional challenges significantly hinder effective service delivery in the Niger State Public Library. It recommends increased funding, provision of modern ICT facilities, continuous staff training, improved conditions of service, and effective library policies to enhance service delivery in public libraries.

Keywords: Public Libraries; Institutional Challenges; Professional Challenges; Librarians; Service Delivery; Niger State

Introduction

Public libraries are important social institutions that provide free access to information, support lifelong learning, promote literacy, and encourage community development. They offer accessible spaces where people can obtain information, develop literacy skills, use digital resources, and participate in educational and cultural activities. In developing countries like Nigeria, public

libraries play a vital role in reducing information inequality and supporting education, especially in rural and underserved communities (Okafor, 2020; Salman et al., 2017).

Despite their importance, many public libraries in Nigeria face structural and operational challenges that limit effective service delivery. These challenges are mainly institutional and professional in nature. Institutional challenges include inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, weak ICT integration, shortage of qualified staff, ineffective policy implementation, and limited government support (Saleh & Aliyu, 2026; Chinedu & Egolum, 2025; Okafor, 2020). Professional challenges include inadequate training opportunities, poor working conditions, lack of continuous professional development, low staff motivation, and insufficient staffing levels (Onwubiko, 2021; Okafor, 2020).

These problems have resulted in outdated collections, limited access to digital resources, low user satisfaction, and declining patronage of public libraries. Inadequate funding, in particular, affects staffing, acquisition of information resources, infrastructure maintenance, and service modernization (Okojie & Okiy, 2020). Similarly, inadequate ICT facilities and skills hinder effective modernization of library services (Akintola, 2021), while weak governance structures and outdated policies contribute to poor service delivery (Abubakar, 2017).

The Niger State Public Library, like many public library systems in Nigeria, operates under similar constraints that affect its ability to provide efficient and user-centered services. Understanding the institutional and professional challenges affecting the library is important for improving service delivery and maintaining its relevance in a changing information environment. Therefore, this study examines the institutional and professional challenges affecting the Niger State Public Library in order to identify gaps and suggest sustainable improvement strategies.

Statement of the Problem

Public libraries are expected to provide accessible and reliable information services that support education, research, and community development. However, the Niger State Public Library, like many public libraries in Nigeria, faces several institutional and professional challenges that affect its effectiveness. Institutional issues such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, limited ICT facilities, shortage of qualified personnel, weak technological integration, and insufficient government support continue to hinder library operations (Chinedu & Egolum, 2025; Okojie & Okiy, 2020). Library personnel also face professional challenges including limited training opportunities, poor working conditions, inadequate professional development, low motivation, heavy workloads, and limited exposure to modern library practices (Salman, 2018; Onwubiko, 2021). These challenges have contributed to poor service delivery, outdated resources, inefficient operations, low user satisfaction, and declining patronage of library services. Despite these challenges, there is limited empirical research that examines both the institutional and professional problems affecting public libraries at the state level in Nigeria. This gap makes it difficult for policymakers and library administrators to develop effective solutions for improving library services and strengthening librarians' professional capacity. Therefore, this study seeks to assess

the institutional and professional challenges affecting the Niger State Public Library and suggest strategies for improvement.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the institutional and professional challenges affecting service delivery in the Niger State Public Library. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Identify the institutional challenges affecting the operations of the Niger State Public Library
2. Examine the professional challenges experienced by library personnel in the Niger State Public Library.
3. Propose strategies for improving library service delivery in the Niger State Public Library.

Literature Review

Institutional challenges remain major barriers to effective public library operations in Nigeria. Studies have identified inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and limited technological facilities as key factors affecting library service delivery. Most public libraries lack sufficient funds to acquire current information resources, maintain facilities, adopt modern technologies, and deliver quality services (Okafor, 2020; Salman et al., 2018; Garba et al., 2019). Inadequate funding also affects staff welfare, collection maintenance, and implementation of innovative services (Idris & Ismaila, 2026; Kasim et al., 2018).

Poor infrastructure is another major challenge facing public libraries. Many libraries operate in deteriorating buildings with limited reading spaces, poor ventilation, inadequate lighting, unstable electricity supply, and insufficient learning facilities (Momodu, 2013; Okafor, 2020; Kasim et al., 2018). These conditions reduce user satisfaction and discourage patronage. Similarly, inadequate ICT facilities have negatively affected library operations. Many public libraries lack computers, internet access, digital databases, and electronic resources, limiting access to timely and relevant information (Okunoye, 2022; Okafor, 2020). The literature also identifies inadequate staffing and shortage of qualified personnel, particularly librarians with ICT and digital literacy skills, as significant institutional challenges (Baada et al., 2020; Onunka et al., 2023). This shortage affects effective organization of information resources and service delivery.

Low public awareness, weak collaboration with educational institutions, and declining reading culture also contribute to poor patronage and limited community engagement (Akor et al., 2021; Isewele-Ishola, 2024). Other institutional problems include bureaucratic bottlenecks, weak policy implementation, and poor governance structures that negatively affect library management and service provision (Salman et al., 2018; Asif & Yang, 2021). Delays in fund release, poor administrative support, and lack of strategic planning further weaken library operations. Socio-economic factors such as poverty, illiteracy, and limited educational opportunities also reduce library usage in many communities (Wheeler, 2021). Collectively, these challenges hinder public

libraries from effectively performing their educational, informational, and community development roles.

Apart from institutional issues, library personnel also face professional challenges that affect their performance. One major challenge is limited access to continuous professional training and development. Many librarians have limited opportunities for workshops, seminars, ICT training, and other professional development programs (Okonkwo et al., 2025; Osiesi et al., 2022). Poor conditions of service also remain a significant challenge. Studies show that low salaries, delayed promotions, lack of incentives, and limited career advancement opportunities negatively affect librarians' morale and productivity (Afolabi & Olubunmi, 2022; Umeji & Anaehobi, 2022).

Inadequate ICT competencies among some library personnel also hinder effective service delivery in the digital era. As libraries increasingly adopt digital resources and services, librarians without sufficient ICT skills struggle to adapt to technological changes (Rajendran & Ladan, 2020). This limits their ability to provide efficient digital services and assist users effectively. In addition, librarians often experience weak professional recognition and limited involvement in institutional decision-making processes (Okafor, 2020). Weak governance structures and absence of clear operational policies further constrain professional effectiveness (Salman et al., 2018; Kasim et al., 2018). These challenges reduce librarians' effectiveness as information managers, educators, and facilitators of knowledge access.

To address these institutional and professional challenges, several studies have proposed different improvement strategies. A major recommendation is increased and sustainable funding from government and relevant stakeholders. Adequate funding would support acquisition of current information resources, infrastructural development, ICT facilities, and staff training programs (Aboh, 2024; Okafor, 2020; Kasim et al., 2018). Improving library infrastructure through renovation of buildings, provision of conducive reading environments, stable electricity supply, and modern learning facilities has also been recommended to enhance service delivery (Lawan et al., 2025). Strengthening ICT infrastructure through computers, internet access, digital collections, and automation systems would further improve access to information and modernize library services (Bello & Adepegba, 2023).

On the professional aspect, continuous training and capacity-building programs are necessary to equip librarians with modern skills required in the digital information environment (Adamu et al., 2021). Regular workshops, seminars, and ICT training can improve librarians' efficiency and adaptability. Improving conditions of service through better salaries, promotion opportunities, incentives, and career development programs has also been recommended to boost staff morale and productivity (Posigha & Seimode, 2015). Furthermore, effective policy reforms and stronger governance structures are necessary to improve accountability, administrative efficiency, and service delivery in public libraries (Abdullahi, 2015). Promoting public awareness and strengthening partnerships with schools, government agencies, and non-governmental organisations can also improve library visibility, relevance, and patronage (Amanze-Unagha &

Unagha, 2023). Therefore, improving public library service delivery requires institutional reforms, professional development, technological advancement, and stronger stakeholder collaboration.

Methodology

The study adopted a quantitative approach using a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 51 professional and paraprofessional staff of the Niger State Library Board, drawn from the headquarters in Minna and five branches in Agaie, Bida, Kontagora, Rijau, and Suleja, based on official library records. Due to the small population, total enumeration (census sampling) was employed, meaning all staff members were included in the study (Okuonghae & Ogamien, 2016). Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into four sections: demographic information, institutional challenges, professional challenges, and strategies for improving service delivery. Responses were measured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument was adapted from previous studies (Kasim et al., 2018; Okafor, 2020) and reviewed by experts in Library and Information Science to ensure validity. Reliability was tested using Cronbach’s alpha, with all constructs exceeding the 0.70 threshold, indicating acceptable internal consistency: institutional challenges (0.82), professional challenges (0.79), and improvement strategies (0.85). Permission was obtained from the Niger State Library Board before data collection. Out of 51 questionnaires distributed, 48 were returned and found usable, giving a response rate of 94.11%. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23 with descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. A benchmark mean score of 2.50 was used to interpret responses, where items with a mean score of 2.50 and above were accepted, while those below 2.50 were rejected.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Respondents Demographic Information

Table 1 presents the demographic information of the respondents used for the study. The results revealed that most respondents were male (68.75%), while females made up 31.25%, indicating a gender imbalance in the public library workforce in Niger State. In terms of age, the majority were above 30 years (66.67%), suggesting a mature workforce, and many had over 10 years of experience (60.41%), reflecting input from experienced staff. However, most respondents were non-professionals (68.75%), with only 31.25% being professionally trained librarians, highlighting a gap in formal expertise. This supports the findings of Estrullo-Suaga et al. (2023) who identified inadequate professional staffing as a major challenge confronting public libraries in Nigeria.

Table 1: Respondent Demographic Information

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	33	68.75%
	Female	15	31.25%
Age	Below 30	16	33.33%
	Above 30	32	66.67%
Professional Status	Professional	15	31.25%

Working Experience	Non-Professional	33	68.75%
	Below 10	19	39.59%
	Above 10	29	60.41%

Institutional Challenges Affecting the Operation of the Niger State Public Library

Table 2 shows that respondents agreed that several institutional challenges affect the effective operation of the Niger State Public Library, as all the items recorded mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50. The highest-ranked challenge was inadequate funding for acquiring new materials and maintaining facilities (Mean = 3.54). This was followed by lack of modern technological facilities such as computers and internet access (Mean = 3.48), and poor infrastructure including outdated buildings and inadequate furniture (Mean = 3.42). These findings suggest that financial and infrastructural problems remain major barriers to effective library service delivery. Respondents also agreed that shortage of trained librarians and staff (Mean = 3.42), poor reading culture among the public (Mean = 3.25), and limited access to updated learning materials (Mean = 3.25) negatively affect library operations.

Other identified challenges include limited collaboration with educational institutions (Mean = 3.19), low public awareness and patronage of library services (Mean = 3.23), lack of clear development policies (Mean = 3.13), and poverty and low educational levels within communities (Mean = 3.02). These findings align with earlier studies which identified inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, shortage of professional staff, and low adoption of technology as major challenges facing public libraries in Nigeria (Idris & Ismaila, 2026; Okafor, 2020). These findings are also consistent with previous studies which reported that inadequate government support and weak policy implementation continue to hinder the growth and effectiveness of public libraries across the country (Okafor, 2020; Okojie & Okiy, 2020). Therefore, improving library services in Niger State requires adequate funding, improved infrastructure, qualified personnel, effective policies, and stronger community engagement.

Table 2: Institutional Challenges Affecting the Operation of the Niger State Public Library

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	Inadequate funding for acquiring new materials and maintaining facilities	28 (58.33)	18 (37.5%)	2 (4.17%)	0 (0.0%)	3.54
2	Lack of modern technological tools like computers and internet access	26 (54.17)	19 (39.58)	3 (6.25%)	0 (0.0%)	3.48
3	Poor infrastructure (outdated buildings and inadequate reading chairs or tables)	22 (45.83%)	24 (50.0%)	2 (4.17%)	0 (0.0%)	3.42
4	Shortage of trained and qualified librarians and staff members	24 (50.0%)	20 (41.67)	4 (8.33%)	0 (0.0%)	3.42
5	Poor reading habits and preference for entertainment over education	19 (39.58)	22 (45.83%)	7 (14.58)	0 (0.0%)	3.25

6	Low public awareness and patronage of public library services	19 (39.58%)	21 (43.75%)	8 (16.66%)	0 (0.0%)	3.23
7	Limited collaboration with educational institutions	18 (37.5%)	23 (47.92%)	5 (10.42)	2 (4.16)	3.19
8	Limited access to updated learning materials like books and journals	20 (41.67%)	22 (45.83%)	4 (8.33%)	2 (4.17)	3.25
9	Poverty and low educational attainment within communities	16 (33.33%)	22 (45.83%)	5 (10.42)	5 (10.4)	3.02
10	Lack of clear policies for the development of public libraries	17 (35.42%)	23 (47.92%)	5 (10.42%)	3 (6.2%)	3.13

Key: 4 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3 = Agree (A), 2 = Disagree (D), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD).

4.3. Professional Challenges Faced by Library Personnel in the Niger State Public Library

Table 3 indicates that library personnel in the Niger State Public Library face several professional challenges that affect effective service delivery and professional growth. The major challenge identified was poor conditions of service, including low salaries and lack of motivation (Mean = 3.62). This was followed by inadequate professional development opportunities for librarians (Mean = 3.56), resistance to adopting new technologies (Mean = 3.56), and inadequate ICT skills among librarians (Mean = 3.52). These findings show that welfare issues and technological limitations greatly affect staff productivity and efficiency. Respondents also agreed that intellectual freedom issues such as censorship and community pressure (Mean = 3.40), inadequate government support for librarians' welfare and professional development (Mean = 3.23), heavy workload caused by shortage of trained staff (Mean = 3.15), and limited involvement in decision-making on budgets and collections (Mean = 3.12) are major professional concerns. The findings agree with earlier studies which reported that poor remuneration, inadequate training opportunities, weak institutional support, and low ICT competence are persistent challenges facing librarians in Nigeria (Salman, 2017; Okafor, 2020). The results also corroborate with studies which observed that lack of continuous professional education, poor staff motivation, and limited technological adaptation reduce librarians' effectiveness and negatively affect the quality of public library services in developing countries (Yaya & Kikelomo, 2015). Therefore, improving librarians' performance requires addressing both welfare and capacity-building challenges.

Table 3: Professional Challenges Faced by Library Personnel in Niger State Public Library

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	Insufficient professional development opportunities for librarians	27 (56.25%)	21 (43.75%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3.56
2	Poor condition of services such as low salaries and lack of motivation	30 (62.5%)	18 (37.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3.62

3	Limited authority in making decisions about the library's budget and collection	19 (39.58%)	20 (41.7%)	5 (10.42)	4 (8.33%)	3.12
4	Resistance to adopting new technologies in the library	29 (60.42)	17 (35.42)	2 (4.17%)	0 (0.0%)	3.56
5	Inadequate ICT skills among librarians	28 (58.33%)	17 (35.42%)	3 (6.25%)	0 (0.0%)	3.52
6	Heavy workloads due to inadequately trained staff	17 (35.42%)	23 (47.92%)	6 (12.5%)	2 (4.17%)	3.15
7	Lack of government support for librarians' professional development and welfare	15 (31.25%)	29 (60.42%)	4 (8.33%)	0 (0.0%)	3.23
8	Issues of intellectual freedom like censorship or community pressures	24 (50.0%)	19 (39.58%)	5 (10.42%)	0 (0.0%)	3.40

Key: 4 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3 = Agree (A), 2 = Disagree (D), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD).

4.4. Strategies for Improving Service Delivery in Niger State Public Library

Table 4 shows that respondents agreed on several strategies for improving service delivery in the Niger State Public Library, as all the items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean. The highest-rated strategy was adequate and sustainable funding for acquiring new library materials and maintaining existing resources (Mean = 3.77). This was followed by improving librarians' conditions of service through better salaries, incentives, and career advancement opportunities a (Mean = 3.73). Respondents also supported improving digital infrastructure such as stable internet access and electricity supply (Mean = 3.63), as well as organizing regular professional training programs to enhance librarians' skills and knowledge (Mean = 3.63). Other important strategies identified include improving library infrastructure such as buildings, seating, and lighting facilities (Mean = 3.56), developing and implementing effective library policies and legislation (Mean = 3.48), increasing public awareness of library resources and services (Mean = 3.40), updating library school curricula to reflect current technological trends (Mean = 3.29), organizing outreach and digital literacy programs (Mean = 3.29), and promoting collaboration among libraries, schools, NGOs, and government agencies (Mean = 3.25). These findings support earlier studies which emphasized that adequate funding, improved staff welfare, technological advancement, policy support, and continuous professional training are necessary for effective public library service delivery (Okafor, 2020; Baada et al., 2020). The findings are also consistent with studies which found that improved infrastructure, investment in ICT facilities, and strengthening librarians' professional capacity significantly enhance public library performance and user satisfaction in Nigeria (Okojie & Okiy, 2020; Oyovwe-Tinuoye et al., 2021).

Table 4: Strategies for Improving Service Delivery in Niger State Public Library

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	Providing adequate and sustainable funding for acquiring new library materials and maintaining existing resources	37 (77.08%)	11 (22.92%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	3.77
2	Improving library infrastructure, including buildings, seating, and lighting facilities	30 (62.50%)	15 (31.25%)	3 (6.25%)	0 (0.00%)	3.56
3	Enhancing digital infrastructure, such as reliable internet access and stable electricity supply	32 (66.67%)	14 (29.17%)	2 (4.17%)	0 (0.00%)	3.63
4	Organizing regular professional training programs to update librarians' skills and knowledge	34 (70.83%)	11 (22.92%)	2 (4.17%)	1 (2.08%)	3.63
5	Updating library school curricula to reflect current professional trends and technological advancements	20 (41.67%)	25 (52.08%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (6.25%)	3.29
6	Improving librarians' conditions of service like clear career progression, competitive salaries, and incentives	35 (72.92%)	13 (27.08%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	3.73
7	Promoting collaboration between libraries, schools, NGOs, and government agencies to expand service reach	19 (39.58%)	23 (47.92%)	5 (10.42%)	1 (2.08%)	3.25
8	Increasing public awareness of available library resources and services	24 (50.00%)	19 (39.58%)	5 (10.42%)	0 (0.00%)	3.40
9	Developing, implementing, and enforcing effective library policies and legislation	27 (56.25%)	17 (35.42%)	4 (8.33%)	0 (0.00%)	3.48
10	Organizing outreach programs, reading campaigns, digital literacy training, and other community-based library services	22 (45.83%)	20 (41.67%)	4 (8.33%)	2 (4.17%)	3.29

Key: 4 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3 = Agree (A), 2 = Disagree (D), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD).

Conclusion

The study examined the institutional and professional challenges affecting service delivery in the Niger State Public Library and identified practical strategies for improvement. The findings revealed that inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, lack of modern technological facilities, shortage of qualified librarians, and weak policy implementation are major institutional challenges limiting effective library operations. The study also established that library personnel face professional challenges such as poor working conditions, inadequate professional development opportunities, insufficient ICT skills, resistance to technological innovation, and limited government support for staff welfare and training. These challenges negatively affect the quality of library services and the overall performance of library personnel. Furthermore, the study identified several strategies capable of improving service delivery, including adequate funding, improved staff welfare, enhanced digital infrastructure, continuous professional training, stronger policy implementation, and increased public awareness of library services. The study therefore concludes that addressing both institutional and professional challenges through sustained government commitment, technological advancement, staff capacity building, and effective policy support is essential for improving the performance and relevance of public libraries in Niger State and Nigeria at large.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to improve service delivery in the Niger State Public Library:

1. The Government and relevant stakeholders should provide adequate and sustainable funding to the Niger State Public Library for the acquisition of current library materials, maintenance of facilities, modernization of library services and improvement of overall library operations.
2. The management of the Niger State Public Library should prioritize the provision of modern ICT facilities such as computers, internet connectivity, digital databases, stable electricity supply, and library automation systems to enhance digital library services and improve access to information resources.
3. The management of the library should recruit more professionally trained librarians and organize regular staff training, workshops, seminars, conferences, and ICT training to improve librarians' professional competence, technological skills, and adaptability to emerging trends in library and information services.
4. Government and library management should improve the welfare and conditions of service of library personnel through better salaries, timely promotions, incentives, and clear career advancement opportunities in order to boost staff morale, motivation, and productivity.
5. The Niger State Public Library should strengthen collaboration with schools, tertiary institutions, non-governmental organizations, and community associations to expand access to library services and support literacy and educational development.

6. Government and library management should formulate and effectively implement clear policies and legislation that support the growth, funding, and modernization of public libraries in Niger State.

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